

A two-headed *Zamenis longissimus*

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Photos by the author

INTRODUCTION

In May 2006, my female *Zamenis longissimus* laid nine eggs, of which one egg was unfertilised. This egg was removed and the rest were incubated. On July 22-23, 2006, seven eggs hatched with perfectly healthy young. Although number eight poked its snout tip out of the eggshell on the same day, the hatchling did not leave the egg. A few days later, the reason became clear.

After four days, the snake from the remaining egg had still not fully hatched so, on July 26, I decided to open the eggshell with a small pair of scissors. The specimen had made a slit in the eggshell (just one snout tip poking out) on the same day as his nest-mates, and wriggled frequently in the days thereafter, but did not get any further. To my amazement, it turned out to be a living dicephalic specimen: it tried to bite at approaching objects with one head, while tongue-flicking with the other.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

My female *Zamenis longissimus* hails from France, Mas Garit, between Ceilhes-et-

Dorsal view of the dicephalic *Zamenis longissimus*.

The dicephalic *Zamenis longissimus* soon after being helped to hatch.

Roconzels and Roqueredonde, dépt. Hérault. She was collected as an apparent adult in 2000. My male was found in 2001 as a two-year old, south of Szob, Hungary, near the border of Slovakia, where the river Ipoly flows into the Danube. The species seems common in this region as during a week's stay we found six snakes of different age classes dead on a stretch of road less than 300 m. Presently the male measures 135-140 cm, the female 110-115 cm.

In 2005 the pair produced nine eggs on 9-10 June, from which eight young snakes hatched after 49 days (there was one unfertilised egg). This year, on June 3-4, there were again nine eggs in total, with one infertile egg. Seven eggs hatched normally after 49-51 days on July 22-23. For both years, eggs were incubated at 27-28°C.

DISCUSSION

The incubation time, as well as the number of eggs per clutch, is as expected for the species (GOMILLE, 2002). BISCHOFF (1993) cites, based on various authors, an extremely broad range of hatchling sizes in *Z. longissimus*: 120-380 mm. Using photographs taken after extracting the dicephalic from the egg, this specimen had an ap-

proximate total length of 270 mm. As its siblings measured about 300-350 mm, the dicephalic was considerably shorter than its nest-mates, which is a familiar finding (Van Wallach, pers. comm.).

As I presumed it would be difficult to raise such a transformed specimen, I decided to euthanise the animal. The species *Z. longissimus* is known to exhibit axial bifurcation (WALLACH, in press), but – as in other snake species – it is quite exceptional (e.g. WALLACH, 2006). A number of possible causes of somatodichotomy have been proposed, including embryonic aberrations, toxins, abnormal temperatures, and exposure to radiation (WALLACH, in press). In the present case, these external factors can be ruled out.

It may be that here the different geographic origin of the parents has something to do with the phenomenon. OLSSON et al. (2004) concluded that in crossings between male and female sand lizards (*Lacerta agilis*) from two different sampling regions, one in Sweden and one in Hungary, risk of gametic incompatibility is unaffected by outbreeding, but offspring from between-population crossings show 300% higher malformation frequency and 10% lower hatching success. The risk of having non-viable offspring increases with the production of daughters, i.e. the hemizygous sex in

A normal *Zamenis longissimus* from the same batch during hatching.

this species (ZW). The sex of this specimen cannot be ascertained as, unfortunately, the preserved dicephalic specimen of *Z. longissimus* got lost in the post while being mailed within Holland.

SUMMARY

A dicephalic *Zamenis longissimus* is described.

SAMENVATTING

Een tweekoppige *Zamenis longissimus* wordt beschreven.

LITERATURE

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